

LONG FIBER REINFORCED POST-CONSUMER THERMOPLASTICS

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SUMMARY: In the United States over 2 million tons of post-consumer carpet (PCC) is land-filled each year. This waste carpet is a useful feedstock for making thermoplastic composites. A key issue is whether the PCC should be separated into its primary thermoplastic base polymers or used as a mixture. By using long fiber reinforcements the deficiencies of a mixed matrix are overcome. Long glass fiber composites with PCC as a matrix are comparable to long glass fiber composites with virgin matrices. Natural fibers and other recycled matrices are included in this assessment. The in-line extrusion compounding of PCC with long fiber reinforcements followed by compression molding of a structural bracket is presented.

KEYWORDS: Thermoplastic nylon, polypropylene, thermoplastic recycling, carpet waste, extrusion compounding, compression molding composites

INTRODUCTION

Landfilling carpet waste, as well as many other thermoplastic wastes, is not sustainable. Reinforcing thermoplastic waste provides a method of upgrading such these materials into useful products. A key issue is whether post-consumer carpet, PCC, should be separated into its primary thermoplastic base polymers or used as a mixture. A composite with a matrix based on a mixture of incompatible polymers is potentially inexpensive. If the reinforcing fibers dominate the composite properties then having a matrix comprised of incompatible polymers can be tolerated. The results presented here indicate composites with attractive properties can be made using a matrix of mixed incompatible polymers.

Most carpet consists of face fiber, usually nylon 66, nylon 6 or polypropylene (PP), with polypropylene backing fabrics and a calcium carbonate filled styrene/butadiene rubber (SBR) latex binder. It is feasible to sort carpets by the type of face fiber, but it is difficult to separate the face fiber from the backing fabrics and latex adhesive. Therefore the focus of this research is to develop inexpensive techniques to recycle post-consumer carpet without separating the face fibers from the backing fabrics.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The post-consumer carpet was obtained from Wellman, Inc. [1,2]. The carpet was diverted from a landfill and sorted by face fiber. A near infrared (NIR) sensor is used to identify the face fiber

within one second. Then the carpet is shredded. Some of the latex, calcium carbonate and dirt drops out between shredding and baling. Wellman, Inc uses this process, plus further finishing (purification) to recover nylon 6 and nylon 66. E glass mat was obtained from Eleison Composites, LLC. [3]. The mat has a low basis weight of 110 g/m² and contains about 10 wt. % of a thermoplastic polyester binder. The glass fiber length is 5 cm.

The shredded carpet was converted into pellets using a NGR A-Class Type 55 VSP Repelletizing system from Next Generation Recyclingmaschinen [4]. To prepare laminates the pellets were converted into a coarse powder using a Wiley mill. Powder was interleaved with glass mats in a 30 cm x 30 cm mold. Sufficient glass mat and powder were used to achieve a laminate with the desired wt % glass. Alternatively, shredded PCC was debulked just below its melting point to create carpet plies which could be interleaved with glass mats. The mold with the material was heated in a 75 ton Wabash press under nominal pressure (< 0.1 MPa) with platen temperatures set 20 to 50 °C above the melting temperature of the highest melting polymer for approximately 25 minutes. A vacuum was drawn on the platen chamber to minimize volatiles and oxidative degradation. Then the press platens were cooled while maintaining a pressure near 0.1 MPa. For the PP PCC the cooling pressure was raised to 0.2 MPa during cooling. Tensile and flexural tests were performed in accord with ASTM D 638 and D 790, respectively. The drop impact tests were performed in accord with ASTM D 3763.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Composite Composition and Properties

One of the first concerns is to determine the composition of the PCC being evaluated. Since all the carpets processed have crystalline polymers as face fibers and backing fabrics, DSC provides a convenient way to check composition. By taking the ratio of the measured latent heat of melting for PP in the PCC to the measured heat of melting for PP fibers from the PCC, the weight fraction of PP in the PCC can be determined. This procedure can be performed for each crystalline polymer present. To provide consistent sampling 15 to 20 grams of the shredded PCC was melt blended in batch mixer (Haake Rheomix 600). Table 1 summarizes these results. Based on the compositions in Table 1 a significant amount of latex binder, calcium carbonate filler and dirt, designated as the remainder in Table 1, has been lost in the shredding process. Thus, the shredded PCC recovered has more than 80 % thermoplastic content.

Table 1: Carpet Compositions Based on DSC Analysis (Weight %)

	PP	N6	N66	Remainder
PP PCC	84	9	0	7
N6 PCC	11	77	0	12
N66 PCC	8	0	81	11

Mechanical properties of the unreinforced carpet materials are presented in Table 2. The strength and modulus values generally exceed virgin PP but are lower than virgin nylons. The failure strains and impact strengths are typical of brittle materials. These trends are expected for incompatible polymer mixtures. The one surprise is the high impact strength for the debulked PP PCC. The high impact energy absorption may be due to unmelted nylon fibers in the PP PCC. The flexural properties are generally higher for the pelletized PCC compared to the debulked

PCC. This improvement is attributed to the venting and melt blending provided by the NGR extrusion. Finally, the flexural strengths of the nylon PCCs are somewhat higher than the PP PCC.

Table 2: Mechanical Properties of Compression Molded and Injection Molded PCC

PCC material and process	Flexural Strength (MPa)	CV (%)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	CV (%)	Drop Impact Strength (J@4.0 mm th)	CV (%)
PP debulk-comp	33	6.5	1.0	41.0	13.9	29.5
-pellet-comp	42	6.2	2.3	16.9	4	29.6
-pellet- inj. m.	31	17.0	0.86	2.6	NA	NA
N6 debulk-comp	56	11.6	1.7	17.2	3.8	10.4
-pellet-comp	70	16.2	2.7	3.7	4.9	39.7
- pellet- inj m.	40	6.6	0.99	6.6	NA	NA
N66 debulk-comp	47	5.5	1.7	23.6	1.1	14.5
-pellet-comp	63	2.7	2.0	14.5	1.7	6.6
-pellet- inj m.	49	8.6	1.4	9.5	NA	NA

NA: not available

Mechanical properties for glass mat reinforced samples are presented in Table 3. The glass mat reinforcement leads to significant improvements in flexural properties and drop impact strength. Based on the properties shown in Table 3, the composites from pelletized PCC have better flexural properties than debulked PCC composites. Also, the flexural strengths of the composites from N66 PCC are higher than the N6 PCC composites which, in turn, are higher than the PP PCC composites. The properties of the nylon PCC composites equal or exceed the properties of commercial glass mat reinforced PP composites [5,6], presented in the last two rows in Table 3.

Table 3: Mechanical Properties of Glass Fiber Reinforced PCC

PCC material – process - % Glass Fiber	Flexural Strength (MPa)	CV (%)	Flexural Modulus (GPa)	CV (%)	Drop Impact Strength (J@ 4.0 mm th)	CV (%)
PP - debulk & comp. mold - 30 %	54	31.8	2.2	33.8	24	16.7
- pellet & comp. mold - 30 %	68	6.1	4.8	5.8	21	2.1
- pellet & comp. mold - 40 %	94	9.8	6.2	6.2	32	12.0
N6 - debulk & comp. mold - 30 %	70	12.7	2.0	32.3	21	7.6
- pellet & comp. mold - 30 %	135	18.1	4.6	26.1	20	20.2
- pellet & comp. mold - 40 %	157	7.1	4.2	12.3	25	18.5
N66 - debulk & comp. mold - 30 %	113	8.2	3.2	6.8	10.5	11.4
- pellet & comp. mold - 30 %	147	8.5	5.7	12.6	8.5	9.5
- pellet & comp. mold - 40 %	179	9.7	8.1	20.8	9.5	15.2
PP Azdel - 32 % [5]	104	NA	4.6	NA	22.7	NA
PP Azdel – 40 % [6]	146	NA	5.5	NA	23.7	NA

The total energy absorbed in the drop impact test is shown in Figure 1. The total energy absorbed has been normalized to 4.0 mm composite thickness to facilitate comparisons. The dominant factor is the amount of glass mat present. It is noteworthy that many of the PCC composites have comparable energy absorption to the commercial sheets from Azdel [5,6].

Fig. 1: Normalized total energy absorbed by PCC composites versus glass mat content.

The notched Izod impact test was performed on most of the composites with 30 and 40 % glass. Complete fractures did not occur. Thus, the Izod impact strength of these composites exceeds 640 J/m.

Wood Fiber Reinforced Composites

Long glass fiber reinforced post-consumer carpet has good strength, stiffness and toughness to suit many applications. However, glass fiber is expensive compared to post-consumer carpet. Therefore a research program has been initiated to look at lower cost wood fiber reinforcements for post-consumer carpet. Wood flour, which has a low aspect ratio and therefore is not considered a reinforcement, is included for comparisons. Wood flour is very inexpensive and is often used in plastic wood products like decking. The fibrous reinforcements considered are kraft pulp, thermomechanical pulp and newsprint. All of these fibers are less expensive than glass fiber, less dense and renewable. Unfortunately, these materials absorb moisture, degrade at typical melt processing temperatures, and are difficult to disperse in viscous thermoplastic matrices.

To minimize degradation during processing some of the fibers were heat treated in an oven for one hour using a nitrogen blanket. The treatment temperature was just above the melt processing temperature. Since cellulose fibers are polar, some of the fibers were sized with a polyurethane emulsion from Hydrosize Technologies, Inc. The wood flour samples were compounded in a Haake 18 mm conical twin screw extruder and then subjected to a course grind. Then tensile and flexural test specimens were injection molded using a 75 ton Sumitomo reciprocating screw

injection molding machine. Tensile and flexural properties are presented in Table 4. The wood flour improved the moduli in all cases. In the polypropylene carpet the wood flour reduced the strength with no sizing and provided essentially equivalent strength to unfilled polypropylene carpet with the sizing present. The wood flour improved the flexural and tensile strengths of the nylon 6 carpet. The wood flour filled nylon 66 samples were too degraded to test.

Table 4: Mechanical Properties of Post-consumer Carpet Reinforced with 40 Wt % Wood Flour

Face Fiber	Heat treat	Sizing	Flex Str.	Flex Mod.	Ten. Str.	Ten. Mod.
		%	MPa	GPa	MPa	GPa
PP/neat	-	-	31	0.9	22	2.0
PP/flour	Yes	No	20	3.2	18	2.4
PP/flour	Yes	3	29	3.4	23	2.6
N6/neat	-	-	40	1.0	36	2.0
N6/flour	Yes	No	78	2.4	40	2.7
N6/flour	Yes	3	66	1.5	44	3.2

Virgin nylon 6 and nylon 6 post-consumer carpet were compounded with different pulps and injection molded. In most cases these samples were prepared by dry blending, injection molding, coarse grinding and injection molding again. All the wood species, flour, thermomechanical pulp (TMP), kraft pulp and newsprint, increased the modulus and strength of the injection molded carpet samples. The strength of the composites did not match virgin nylon 6. The composite samples all had some porosity, either from wood degradation or residual moisture, which may be limiting the development of higher strengths in the composites. In particular, the TMP and kraft pulps were expected to provide higher strength composites compared to wood flour due to higher fiber aspect ratios. It is possible that these pulps were not sufficiently dispersed in the nylon 6 to realize the benefits of having higher aspect ratios. There aren't sufficient differences in properties to determine whether heat treating the pulps in advance is necessary. Also, the sizing may not be necessary since nylon is similar to polyurethane.

Table 5: Mechanical Properties of Nylon 6 with Different Pulps @ 40 wt %

Matrix	Pulp	Heat Treatment	Sizing	Flex Str.	Flex Mod.	Ten. Str.	Ten. Mod.
			%	MPa	GPa	MPa	GPa
Virgin	-	-	-	115	1.5	56	1.6
Carpet	-	-	-	40	1.0	36	2.0
Carpet	Flour	Yes	3	66	1.5	44	3.2
Carpet	TMP	No	-	62	3.8	39	3.2
Carpet	TMP	No	3	53	4.7	30	2.9
Carpet	TMP	Yes	3	50	4.3	31	3.0
Carpet	Kraft	No	3	46	3.5	40	2.9
Carpet	Kraft	Yes	3	49	4.3	38	3.2
Carpet	Newsprint	No	3	54	2.9	32	3.1

Since degradation of the wood is evident in the nylon 6 composites the current focus of this research is on minimizing the thermal history. This can be accomplished by doing in-line

compounding followed immediately by compression molding, similar to the steps used to make the brackets described in the next section. The current difficulty in pursuing this approach is consistently metering the pulp to the extruder. Modified feeding systems are being investigated.

Products from Reinforced Post-Consumer Carpet

Based on the properties of glass fiber reinforced PCC, a number of products are being developed. One product is structural lumber. This lumber differs from decking because it is much stiffer and stronger. Therefore this lumber can be used as the support structure for decks. Figure 2 shows the extrusion of a plastic board using glass fiber reinforced nylon 6 PCC.

Fig. 2: Extrusion of 30 % glass fiber reinforced nylon 6 PCC as a substitute for structural lumber

A variety of compression molded products are being developed. One approach is based on making sheets of glass mat reinforced thermoplastic which is subsequently reheated and molded. The second approach uses in-line molding of the hot extrudate. The latter approach is particularly useful for nylon based PCC since no additional drying is needed. Some of the products being explored include automotive bumper beams and shipping pallets.

Georgia Composites is evaluating a number of these options with partial support from CARE [7,8]. The in-line molding has been demonstrated at Georgia Tech. A 30 mm twin screw extruder from NFM Welding Engineers was used to melt PCC, add 25 mm glass fibers, vent volatiles and extrude a 25 mm diameter hot log. The hot log was cut at regular time intervals, folded and immediately compression molded into brackets for a “Z-bar” clothing rack. The rack is shown in Figure 3. The brackets are used to hold the vertical tubes. The bracket shown in Figure 3 is a prototype made by stereolithography. A compression molded bracket is shown in Figure 4.

CONCLUSIONS

Post-consumer carpet (PCC) can be converted into glass mat composites with properties comparable to commercial glass mat composites. The nylon PCC composites have better properties than PP PCC composites. Since PCC matrices are inexpensive a variety of high

Fig. 3: Z-bar clothing rack with plastic bracket. The current welded tube construction (in yellow) is behind.

Fig. 4: Brackets molded from post-consumer carpet with 20 % glass fiber with an original length of 25 mm. The bracket on the left came from polypropylene carpet and the one on the right from nylon 6.

volume applications are being explored in order to divert PCC from landfills. In collaboration with Georgia Composites, in-line compounding of long glass fiber with PCC followed immediately by compression molding of brackets has been demonstrated. In more recent work a variety of wood fiber/PCC composites have been extruded and injection molded.

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